

Seasonal pattern in atmospheric pollutants in Rome during the decade 2013-2023

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I present a script in R that analyses measures of the following pollutants, in Rome for the specified range of years: BENZENE, CO, NO, NO₂, NO_x, O₃, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, SO₂. Data are automatically retrieved from the website of ARPA Lazio and stored in a list available for further analysis. After normalization of data, the script generates a plot of the time series of all the covariates and it also generates a correlation table, as shown in the following pictures. A plot for mean values over the available years is also generated. A moving mean of 7 days has been employed.

Repository: <https://github.com/paolomaccallini-hub/Pollutants>

Rome - year: 2013

Rome - year: 2014

Rome - year: 2015

Rome - year: 2016

Rome - year: 2017

Rome - year: 2018

Rome - year: 2019

Rome - year: 2020

Rome - year: 2021

Rome - year: 2022

Rome - year: 2023


```

# file name: Pollution
#
# Rome, April 7th, 2024
#
library(car)
library(runner) # for moving mean
library(lubridate) # for make_date()
library(corrplot) # for corrplot
source("Pollution_func.R") # a set of subroutines
#
# acquire paths
#
pollutants<-c("BENZENE","CO","NO","NO2","NOX","O3","PM2.5","PM10","SO2")
years<-as.character(seq(2013,2023))
url.0<-"https://www.arpalazio.net/main/aria/sci/basedati/chimici/BDchimici/RM/MedieGiornaliere/"
path.0<-getwd( )
    
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setwd(path.0)
#
nd<-7 # number of days for the moving mean
#
# load, moving mean
#
e.list<-load.mm(url.0,path.0,nd,pollutants,years)
#
# data normalization
#
for (i in 1:length(years)) {
  for (j in 1:length(pollutants)) {
    e.list[[i]][j]<-as.vector(scale(e.list[[i]][j]))
  }
}
#
# plot for each year
#
for (i in 1:length(years)) {
  fun.plot(e.list[[i]],years[i],pollutants)
}
#
# mean over all the available years and plot
#
e.data<-e.list[[1]]
for (p in 1:length(pollutants)) {
  for (d in 1:length(e.list[[1]][,1])) {
    vec<-c()
    for (y in 1:length(years)) {
      vec[y]<-e.list[[y]][d,p]
    }
    e.data[d,p]<-mean(vec,na.rm=T)
  }
}
fun.plot(e.data,paste(years[1],"-",years[length(years)]),pollutants)

```

```

# file name: Pollution_func
#
# Rome, April 9th, 2024
#
#-----
# Data loading and moving mean
#-----
#
load.mm<-function(url.0,path.0,nd,pollutants,years) {
  mymatrix<-matrix(nrow=365,ncol=length(pollutants))
  e.data<-as.data.frame(mymatrix)
  e.list<-list()
  for (y in 1:length(years)) {
    for (j in 1:length(pollutants)) {
      name.file<-gsub(" ", "", paste("RM_",pollutants[j],"_",years[y],"_gg.txt"))
      url<-gsub(" / ", "/", paste(url.0,"/",name.file))
      path<-gsub(" / ", "/", paste(path.0,"/",name.file))
      download.file(url,path,method="auto") # download file from website
      mydata<-read.csv(file=name.file,header=T,sep="")
      file.remove(path)
      colnames(mydata)<-gsub("X", "", colnames(mydata))
    }
  }
}

```

```

c.col<-2
for (k in 3:length(mydata[1,])) {
  if (as.numeric(colnames(mydata)[k])<60) c.col<-c.col+1
}
mydata<-mydata[,1:c.col] # stations within Rome
mydata<-replace(mydata,mydata==-999,NA)
for (k in 1:length(mydata[1,])) {
  mydata[k,3]<-mean(as.numeric(mydata[k,3:c.col]),na.rm=T) # mean over all the stations
}
days<-length(mydata[,1])
for (d in 1:days) {
  e.data[d,j]<-mydata[d,3]
}
e.data[,j]<-runner(e.data[,j],k=nd,f=mean,simplify=T) # moving mean
colnames(e.data)[j]<-pollutants[j]
}
e.list[[y]]<-e.data
}
return(e.list)
}
#
#-----
# Plot of normalized diagrams for pollutants and table of correlations
#-----
#
fun.plot<-function(df,str,pollutants) {
  len<-length(pollutants)
  col.names<-c("orange","black","blue","cyan","magenta","red3","azure2","gray","yellow")
  file.str<-gsub(" ","",paste("RM_",str,".jpeg"))
  jpeg(file.str,quality=100,res=150,width=1500,height=1500)
  par(mfrow=c(2,1))
  massimo<-max(df,na.rm=T)
  minimo<-min(df,na.rm=T)
  days<-length(df[,1])
  for (j in 1:length(pollutants)) {
    vec<-as.data.frame(df[,j])
    xlab<-paste("days - moving mean on",nd,"days")
    plot(seq(1:days),vec[,1],xlim=c(1,days+100),ylim=c(minimo,massimo),type="l",lty=1,
         col=col.names[j],lwd=2.5,xlab=xlab,ylab="normalized measures")
    if (j<length(pollutants)) par(new=T)
  }
  #
  months<-c()
  months[1]<-1
  vector<-c()
  vector[1]<-1
  for (k in 2:days) {
    months[k]<-month(make_date(2023,1,1)+days(k-1))
    if (months[k]>months[k-1]) vector[months[k]]<-k
  }
  #
  title(paste("Rome - year:",str))
  abline(v=vector,lty=2)
  abline(h=0,lty=2)
  legend("right",legend=pollutants,col=col.names,lwd=rep(2.5,len),lty=rep(1,len),
        bg="white")
  vector<-vector+10
}

```

```
text(x=vector,y=c(rep(minimo,12)),
     labels=c("Jan","Feb","Mar","Apr","May","Jun","Jul","Aug","Sep","Oct","Nov","Dic"))
corrplot(cor(df),method="color",addCoef.col="black",number.digits=2,
         number.cex=0.8)
dev.off()
}
```